

Two Conservation of Momentum Equations and Quantum Mechanics

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We consider the one dimensional reflection-refraction of a photon at an n_1 - n_2 (index of refraction) interface and argue that there are two conservation of momentum equations. The first is a classical statement which is based on the dynamics of a steady state view of the problem.

The second is based on the idea that time is removed from the problem in order to create a steady state view in the first place. With time removed, $P(x)$ represents a probability to find a photon at x and this can have nothing to do with motion, yet p exists and so as argued in previous notes one must have $P(p,x)$ and $P(-p,x)$, or $P(p,x)P(-p,x)=P(x)$ so that p cancels i.e. $P(p,x)=\exp(ipx)$. The two conservation of momentum equations cannot be independent and so one this leads to a conservation of $\exp(ipx)$ terms and one has quantum mechanics existing as a square root of flux type of probability in order for the two momentum equations to be consistent.

The issue with the classical approach is that two different probabilities are used, flux/c to represent the static probability to reflect/refract and flux as the probability for p . Thus, what should be two independent equations become the same equation. One requires the quantum approach which introduces the same probability $\exp(ipx)$ allowing for two independent equations, one containing p and the other not.

One Dimensional Reflection-Refraction of Photons

One dimensional reflection-refraction of a photon at an n_1 - n_2 (index of refraction junction) is a dynamic problem, but it is also a probabilistic one. One may immediately write a static equation:

$$1 = \text{Probability}(\text{reflect}) + \text{Probability}(\text{refract}) \quad ((1))$$

We argue that this is a static equation because one may take whatever amount of time one wants to measure these probabilities. One does not have to worry about c_1 and c_2 , the speed of light of the incident or reflected photons when making the measurement. The fact that ((1)) is a static equation indicates the issue with a classical approach. One has on the one hand the static ((1)) and on the other hand a flux dynamical picture for p at the same time. These two scenarios are in fact not independent, but one and the same.

It is possible, however, to create an idealized steady state picture of this problem. This idealized state does not exist in nature, because one must make numerous trial runs in time. It is possible that the first three photons refract, then two reflect then another four refract etc. This is not a steady state picture. Furthermore, one must consider an average in time to have reflected and refracted photons together. Thus, we argue that a steady state picture is an idealized one based on removing the details of what happens in time (i.e. reflection/refraction in a nonuniform manner) from the scenario. Nevertheless, dynamical variable c (speed of light) and the notion of a dynamic flux do not disappear. Thus, there is a kind of inconsistency. On the one hand, one

considers a problem with time removed in order to say that one has a steady stream of incident, reflected and refracted photons and on the other, one focus on dynamic (time based) ideas like speed and flux. These two approaches leads to two different conservation of momentum equations which must be compatible because there is only one conservation of momentum statement.

Steady State Conservation of Momentum

One may imagine a steady state conservation of momentum picture. If a photon reflects, this means that $p \rightarrow -p$ and a force must cause this. If $p \rightarrow p_2$, as in refraction, a force is again responsible. If one considers an average in time, one may argue for action-reaction, i.e. for the average of the force to disappear and for conservation of average momentum to exist. The question is: What does one use for probabilities?

If an incident particle becomes a reflected one, there is a certain probability for this to occur (static), but in a steady stream picture one considers probability to be based on flux. If particles are created with less probability, but they move fast then in a given dt , they may all move out of a box. If another set of particles are created with more probability throughout the box, but move more slowly, only some will come out in dt . It then appears as if they were created with less probability. Thus, flux seems to be the probability measure, not the actual probability to create the particles. This leads to:

$$AA p - BBp = CC p_2 \quad ((2)) \quad \text{where } AA, BB, CC \text{ are incident, reflected and refracted fluxes}$$

and $p, -p, p_2$ the corresponding momenta. Thus, in this dynamic problem, one actually has a dynamic probability, namely flux.

Time Removed

Interestingly, the steady state picture given above with flux as probability, is a mathematical idealization of a physical problem which has time removed (except for the notion of velocity). If one sends a single photon to the n_1 - n_2 junction, it either reflects or refracts. Experimentally, the first three photons may reflect, the next two refract the next four reflect etc. A steady stream picture is an idealization with the actual physical events in time replaced with numerous incident, reflected and refracted photons.

Even though a steady stream involves each photon moving with a speed c , as soon as one photon moves from its position, it is replaced by another. Thus, there is a static probability in space, $P(x)$, which is a constant and has nothing to do with the speed c . If one wishes to create a probability $P(p,x)$ for this scenario, then $P(x)$ is still static and one must consider $P(p,x)$ together with $P(-p,x)$ i.e. $P(p,x)P(-p,x)=P(x)=\text{constant}$ or $P(p,x)=\exp(ipx)$. This leads to a very different probability for p and x . Why does one want a $P(p,x)$? It is required if one wishes to calculate a conservation of momentum equation not based on the flux or particles in a box picture. This lead to:

$$D1 p \exp(ipx) + D2 (-p) \exp(-ipx) = D3 p_2 \exp(ip_2x) \text{ at } x=0 \quad ((3))$$

In other words, one now has two conservation of momentum equations, ((2)) and ((3)), but there is only one concept of conservation of momentum. Thus, the two equations must be compatible. The way to make them compatible is to have:

$$D1 \exp(ipx) + D2 \exp(-ipx) = D3 \exp(ip2x) \text{ at } x=0 \quad ((4))$$

where $D1=A$, $D2=B$ and $D3=C$.

In other words, one has two equations ((3)) and ((4)) which are required to create ((2)). These two equations have two unknowns, B and C if A is known and so one may be used to calculate the reflection and refraction probabilities using ((3)) and ((4)), while one cannot calculate them using ((2)) alone. Why should this be the case? One started with two conservation of momentum equations? It seems that ((4)) represents another conservation equation namely that of $\exp(ipx)$ s with weights. Thus, ((3)) and ((4)) represent two conservation equations.

This then leads to the question: Why does the classical flux approach lead to one equation (only conservation of momentum) while the $P(p,x)$ approach to two equations? The $P(p,x)$ approach yields a probability $\exp(ipx)$ which contains p and is a function of x. Thus, one may apply continuity of the function and its first derivative at the $n1-n2$ x junction point.

The flux probability approach only holds at the $n1-n2$ x junction for conservation of momentum. The issue is that there is no flux conservation equation to go along with it as $AA \neq BB+CC$. One may note that the steady state picture is an idealized one and is only used to establish conservation of momentum on average. This conservation of momentum equation is equivalent to $1 = \text{Probability}(\text{reflect}) + \text{Probability}(\text{refract})$ for the photon, so the two equations which one might have wished for are in fact one and the same. This shows that the classical view does not contain enough information, we argue. The reason for this problem is that in the classical view, two different probabilities are used, not one which would lead to two independent equations. In particular, flux/c is the static probability to reflect/refract, but flux is the probability linked with p. Thus, by having two different probabilities used in two equations, the two equations become the same while the quantum mechanical approach uses the same probability allowing one to create two independent equations, one without p and one with p.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that one may write two conservation of momentum equations for the same problem, photon one dimensional reflection-refraction. The first equation is a classical one based on flux as a probability. The product of flux times momentum is, however, the probability (incident, reflected or refracted) because $E=pc$ and E is the same for all. Thus, one might have expected two equations, but these two coincide. This shows that the dynamic picture (i.e. one using fluxes) does not contain enough information or seems to miss the idea that this problem is really one in x with time removed. The entire steady state scenario is based on averaging in time and creating an ideal probability, i.e. steady stream. In practice, two particles may reflect, three refract etc. If one really has the notion of x with no time, then $P(x)$ static should represent probability in x, yet there is still p present and it changes. One would expect $P(p,x)$, but this

means one must have $P(p,x)P(-p,x) = P(x)$ or $P(p,x)=\exp(ipx)$ so that p and $-p$ cancel in an exponent. With an $\exp(ipx)$ probability, one may create a momentum conservation equation: $D1\exp(ipx)p + D2(-p)\exp(-ipx) = D3 \exp(ip2x) p^2$ at $x=0$ and this must be consistent with the classical flux one. This leads to $D1=A$, $D2=B$, $D3=C$ and $D1\exp(ipx) + D2\exp(-ipx) = D3 \exp(ip2x)$ at $x=0$. These two equations allow one to solve the problem.

The real issue with the steady state picture is that flux/c yields probability, but this is the same as $\text{flux } p$ meaning that two different probabilities exist, namely the static flux/c and flux which is used with p . Thus, one cannot have a probability conservation independent of momentum conservation in the flux view and must use the quantum mechanical approach.